

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

RADIOACTIVITY, ECOSYSTEMS AND BIODIVERSITY

Ozturk M.,

*Department of Botany and Centre for Environmental Studies, Ege University,
Izmir, Turkiye*

Gul A.,

*Department of Plant Biotechnology, Atta-ur-Rahman School of Applied Biosciences (ASAB), National University of Sciences and Technology (NUST),
Islamabad, Pakistan*

Siddique I.,

*Department of Plant Biotechnology, Atta-ur-Rahman School of Applied Biosciences (ASAB), National University of Sciences and Technology (NUST),
Islamabad, Pakistan*

Altay V.

*Department of Biology, Faculty of Science and Arts,
Hatay Mustafa Kemal University,
Hatay, Turkiye*

Abstract

Radioactivity is a natural phenomenon that has both direct and indirect effects on ecosystems and biodiversity. Radioactive substances are emitted by natural as well as anthropogenic sources which can enter ecosystems through various pathways such as air, water and soil. Once introduced into the environment, they can impact organisms at different trophic levels from microorganisms to plants and animals. The effects of radioactivity on biodiversity are multifaceted and include alterations in species abundance, composition and genetic diversity. Furthermore, radiation can induce genetic mutations and alter reproductive processes, potentially leading to long-term effects on populations and ecosystems. Research has shown that certain organisms possess remarkable adaptive mechanisms to cope with radiation exposure. These adaptations involve DNA repair mechanisms, antioxidant defense systems and enhanced tolerance to radiation-induced stress. Further research is required to unravel the intricate processes underlying the responses of different species and ecosystems to radioactivity, as well as to develop effective strategies for monitoring and conserving biodiversity in radioactively contaminated environments. This study provides an overview of understanding of radioactivity, its effects ecosystems and biodiversity and highlighting key radioactive accidents and research findings about the radioactive contamination effects.

Keywords: radioactivity, ecological interactions, radioactive contamination, Chernobyl disaster, Fukushima disaster.

Introduction

Radioactivity is a property displayed by particular kinds of matter where radiation, energy and subatomic particles are emitted instinctively from atomic nuclei. When an unstable nucleus undergoes decay, it emits certain particles or forms of electromagnetic energy to become more stable. This property is present in some naturally occurring elements and artificially produced isotopes. This phenomenon was first observed in 1896 by Henri Becquerel when he was experimenting with uranium salt. Later, it was discovered that all uranium compounds are radioactive due to the uranium's inherent radioactivity. In 1898, Marie Curie and her husband discovered two naturally occurring radioactive elements named, radium and polonium. The three main processes of radioactivity are alpha decay, beta decay, and gamma decay. In 1934, it was discovered that radioactivity could also be induced in ordinary matter through artificial transmutation. The rate of radioactive decay is measured in terms of half-life, which is the time required for half of a given quantity of the isotope to decay. Half-life can range from more than 1024 years to less than 10-23 seconds. The daughter isotope produced by a radioactive decay process may also be unstable and undergo further decay until a stable nuclide is formed [1].

The origin of life on earth is due to radiations present on earth which provoked photochemical transformations for life forms sustainability. These radiations are classified into ionizing and non-ionizing rays and are used for human advantage but in some cases they are potential hazard to human and environment due to their misuse [2]. Our environment is exposed to natural ionic radiations for very long time specially the radionuclides are present in large amount which are hazardous to environment and all life forms [3]. The radioactive pollution reported in the environment is said to be spread by human activities, but studies have also shown the participation of natural radioactive materials in causing radioactive pollution [4]. Some anthropogenic causes of radioactive contamination are radioactive elements mining, unsafe nuclear industrial waste disposal, improper disposal of medically utilized radioisotopes and several nuclear power plants situated around the world [5]. Human activities have caused significant harm to the planet and its biodiversity. The presence of high levels of radioactive elements in the environment, which can occur naturally or due to human activities such as mining and nuclear waste disposal, poses a threat to both the ecosystem and human health. Radionuclides like ^{238}U and ^{226}Ra can be found in the

Earth's crust, while anthropogenic activities can increase the concentration of radionuclides like ^{137}Cs , ^{129}I , ^{99}Tc , and Pu [6]. Prolonged exposure to radioactive contaminated sites can cause various types of cancers in humans and animals due to the carcinogenic properties of radionuclides [5]. The research in radioecology has shed light on the behavior of radionuclides in plants and the risks associated with food chain transfer. Studies have also explored the passing of radionuclides to crops and consumable plants, as ingestion of these materials can pose a serious health risk [7,8]. The protection of biodiversity, ecosystems, and the environment is crucial in ensuring the provision of ecosystem services that are necessary for food security and the well-being of all living beings. To mitigate radioactive pollution, there is a need for bioremediation technologies that are both practical and cost-effective. These technologies should be capable of decontaminating affected lands and water to benefit humankind. The current chapter summarizes the effects of radioactivity on ecosystem and biodiversity and measures that can be taken to decontaminate climate from excess radiation.

Discovery of radioactivity

Towards the ending of the 19th century, the notion that the matter could radiate radiation, apart from being heated or subjected to high voltage, was virtually non-existent. Light, illustrated by the theory of Maxwell but not quantized yet, stood as the best understood form of radiation. The nature of cathode rays, observed by the German physicist Johann Hittorf in year 1869, remained a topic of debate. Moreover, the newly discovered radiation in 1895 by Röntgen, which he aptly named X-rays, remained shrouded in mystery. However, within the subsequent years, a groundbreaking revelation emerged about the radioactivity phenomenon. The seeds of this finding were planted by Henri Poincaré, who was intrigued by X-rays [9]. The discovery of radioactivity stands as a monumental achievement in the annals of scientific history. Pioneering researchers such as Henri Becquerel, Marie Curie, and Pierre Curie led the charge in unraveling the mysteries of this captivating phenomenon. In 1896, Henri Becquerel serendipitously stumbled upon radioactivity while conducting experiments with phosphorescent materials. He observed that uranium salts, even when shielded from light, had the ability to expose photographic plates. This accidental finding sparked a scientific revolution, opening the door to a new realm of inquiry. Marie Curie, together with her husband Pierre Curie, further delved into the study of radioactivity. They coined the term "radioactivity" and dedicated themselves to isolating and characterizing new radioactive elements. Through meticulous work, they discovered polonium and radium, forever changing the scientific landscape [9,10]. Then, André Debierne identified actinium [11]. Gerhard Carl Schmidt discovered thorium emits radiations [12]. In 1903, scientists were unaware of the existence of isotopes or the presence of a nucleus within the atom. At that time, radioactivity was regarded as an intrinsic nuclear property. However, the credit for uncovering the ability to generate radioactive species, specifically radioactive isotopes, across all chemical elements goes to Irène, the daughter of Pierre

and Marie Curie, and her husband, Frédéric Joliot. Their groundbreaking work brought forth a new understanding of the atomic world and the diverse possibilities of radioactive isotopes [13,14].

Historical incidents of radioactive dangers

The dangers associated with radioactive materials were experienced by people long before the discovery of the phenomena of radioactivity. Historical accounts indicate instances where individuals working with certain naturally occurring radioactive substances, such as uranium ore, experienced adverse health effects without fully knowing the underlying cause. In central Europe the mines that used for their heavy metal presence since medieval period were so much radioactive that the workers suffered from dangerous lung illness which was later diagnosed to be lung cancer and the cause of which was known to be radon [15]. In 1556, 400 years before this incident Georgius Agricola published his book titled "De Re Metallica". He discussed about the high death rate of the miners working in mines [16]. Radioactive materials were utilized before even knowing about their radioactive effects like Welsbach gas mantle in 1885 was developed in which thorium oxide was used. In various parts of the world natural radioactivity has been considered advantageous in health. There is no satisfactory answer to how this custom started but the use of mineral water in spas became so popular as long ago in Roman times. After the discovery of radioactivity phenomena, these mineral waters were tested which demonstrated the high number of radioactive elements in them. May be due to this fact it raised the idea that this newly discovered and mysterious property of the matter was the cause why these waters were considered to possess curing abilities. The discovery that radium radiation could cause the destruction of cancer tissues enhanced its popularity in a short period of time and different spas started to display radioactivity level of their water. Labels on bottled water in many countries still display the radioactivity level of the spring from which water was acquired. In United States and Austria, the high concentration of radioactivity in old mines and radioactivity in sand of Brazilian beaches have allured tourists who thought that natural radioactivity can heal arthritis and various other types of diseases [17].

In early 1920 to 1940, radon and radium found their way into the realm of medical faddism. Radium was intravenously injected for many illnesses but instead of curing it resulted in the development of bone cancer in many patients. Devices that were given to use at home resulted in the addition of radon to drinking water [18]. One notable example is the story of the Radium Girls in the early 20th century. These women worked in radium dial factories and used to paint watch dials with radium-based paint. They would often lick the paintbrushes to create a fine tip, ingesting small amounts of radium. Over time, many of these workers developed severe health issues, including radiation sickness, bone fractures and even death. However, at that time, the connection between their health problems and radioactivity was not yet fully understood. The research of Henri Becquerel, Marie Curie and Pierre Curie in the late 19th and early 20th century, shed light on

the nature of radiation and the risks associated with radioactive materials. This scientific understanding eventually led to the development of safety measures and regulations to protect individuals from the dangers of radiation exposure [19]. It is worth noting that historical instances of radiation related dangers, like those mentioned, contributed to the growing body of knowledge that eventually led to the discovery and understanding of radioactivity as a scientific concept.

Types of radioactivity

The initial investigations about natural radioactivity related to uranium and thorium ores revealed the existence of two forms of radioactivity which are alpha decay and beta decay. Later gamma rays were also explained. There are three primary types of radioactivity. First is alpha decay in which alpha particles are emitted by an unstable atom, which contains two protons and two neutrons. This emission results in reduction of atomic mass of parent nucleus by four and atomic number reduction by two. Alpha particles possess positive charge and are relatively heavy and large. They can be stopped by a few centimeters of air or a sheet of paper. Beta decay occurs when beta particles are emitted by an unstable atomic nucleus. There are two kinds of beta particles, Beta-plus particles (positrons) and Beta-minus particles (electrons). In beta-plus decay, a proton in the nucleus transforms into a neutron by releasing a positron and neutrino. In the beta-minus decay, a neutron transforms into a proton with the release of an electron and an antineutrino. Beta particles have a negative or a positive charge and are smaller than alpha particles. They can penetrate deeper into matter than alpha particles and can be stopped by aluminum or plastic of a few millimeters thickness. Gamma decay also recognized as gamma radiation results in the liberation of photons possessing high energy called gamma rays. They are electromagnetic radiations which neither have charge nor mass. They are released from an atomic nucleus during the transition from an excited state to a lower-energy state. Gamma rays have high penetration power and can pass through several centimeters of lead or many meters of air. These types of radioactivity are related to the decay of unstable atomic nuclei and play a vital role in various natural and artificial radioactive activities [20,21].

Sources of radioactive contamination

Radiation has been an ever-present natural phenomenon around us in various forms. Life has evolved in an environment with substantial levels of ionizing radiation. Numerous radioisotopes occur naturally, originating during the solar system's formation and the interaction of cosmic rays with atmospheric molecules. For instance, tritium is a radioisotope formed through this interaction. Potassium-40 can be found in several common foods like carrots, red meats, Brazil nuts, white potatoes, bananas and lima beans. Certain radioisotopes, such as potassium-40, polonium-210 and carbon-14 are naturally found in the human body. The average annual dose from natural background radiation is approximately 2.4 mSv globally. According to the United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation (UNSCEAR), there are four major sources that exist when it comes to natural radiation i.e.,

terrestrial radiation, cosmic radiation and intakes of naturally present radionuclides via ingestion and inhalation [22]. Natural radiation is most vital contributor to yearly disclosure of global population. Natural radiation plays a vital role in determining the overall radiation exposure levels, emphasizing the need to measure and evaluate its presence in soil [23]. There exist 1500 nuclides which are radioactive in nature. Radionuclides are naturally found in our environment [24]. The primary source of radiation to human is gamma radiations which originated from radionuclides [25]. Most of the dose attributed to ionizing radiations result from natural sources of radiation. In most countries in Europe, primary drinking water source is groundwater, which can add radiations to water due to the dissolution of naturally found radionuclides from bedrock [26]. Radon and Thoron which are alpha emitters largely contribute to radiation exposure. These are decay outcomes of Uranium (238U) and thorium (232Th) usually present in soils and rocks that contaminate the atmosphere and results in radiation exposure to people living near mining areas [27]. Naturally occurring radioactive materials, such as radon gas, can be present in rocks, soil, and water, can seep into buildings, particularly in areas with high radon concentrations, leading to indoor contamination [28].

Agricultural lands and groundwater are frequently reported to be contaminated by radioactive materials. Radioactive pollution is caused by both natural as well as anthropogenic activities. The primary causes of radioactive pollution are unprotected mining of radioactive substances, unsafe disposal of nuclear industrial waste, military applications, improper disposal of medical radioisotopes, the presence of over 400 nuclear power plants worldwide, and the use of phosphate fertilizers in agriculture [5]. Testing of historical nuclear weapons has left radioactive residues in the atmosphere, soil and water in certain areas. Certain minerals and ores, like radium, uranium and thorium, possess radioactive elements naturally. Mining and extraction practices can release these radioactive materials into the environment if not handled in a proper manner. Careless handling, storage or disposal of radioactive substances used in medical, industrial or research applications can contribute to contamination if not properly managed. Industrial accidents like transportation accidents, can result in the release of radioactive substances into the environment. Well known nuclear incidents, like the Fukushima disaster year 2011 and Chernobyl disaster in 1986 resulted in significant radioactive contamination in the surrounding regions [29]. Radioactivity exists in various forms and the level of risk and exposure depends on factors like type and amount of radioactive material, distance from the source, time duration and nature of exposure. Proper safety measures are mandatory to minimize the risks associated with radioactivity.

Pathway of contamination

The discharge of elements having radioactive property into the air poses risks to ecosystem, as these materials can be deposited on soil and vegetation. The pathway of radioactive contamination refers to the routes via which radioactive materials can spread and

potentially impact the environment and living organisms. Radioactive materials can be released into the atmosphere through nuclear accidents, nuclear weapon testing or industrial processes. These materials can spread over long distances through air currents, leading to contamination of air, soil, vegetation and water bodies. Humans may face internal exposure when radionuclides are absorbed by plants. The fate of radioactivity is generally unaffected by translocation, which refers to the movement of radionuclides within plants. However, the physiological properties of radionuclides in plants at the deposition time can influence their translocation. Plants have two transport systems, the xylem and the phloem, which play a role in the movement of radionuclides. Wind also plays a vital role in radionuclides washout from plants and soil. Radioactive substances can contaminate soil via direct deposition from atmosphere, water sources or through soil erosion and sedimentation. Resuspension takes place when debris and particles are lifted from the soil surface into atmosphere by wind, soil cultivation and human activities. This process actively contributes to the radionuclides suspension in the soil, leading to their redistribution within the soil profile and affecting their concentration over time [30]. Radioactive materials can enter water bodies via direct release from nuclear facilities, runoff from contaminated areas or leaching from underground sources. Once in the water, they can be transported downstream, affecting aquatic organisms and potentially contaminating drinking water bodies [31]. These enter the food chain through plant uptake from contaminated soil or water. Animals that consume these contaminated plants can accumulate these radioactive substances in their tissues. When humans consume contaminated food, they can be exposed to radiation [32]. Radioactive substances present on surfaces, such as buildings, equipment or vegetation, can come into direct contact with organisms or humans. Medical diagnostic and therapeutic procedures which involves the use of radioactive substances, such as X-rays, CT scans or nuclear medicine, can expose individuals to radiation [33,34].

Radioactive contamination incidents

Several large scale and small incidents occurred that resulted in liberation of radioactive substances to environment. Some of them are: Mayak Disaster (1957), an eruption at the Mayak Production Association nuclear facility in the Soviet Union (Russia) released a significant number of radioactive materials into the environment. The incident was initially covered up, resulting in significant health consequences for nearby communities [35]. Three Mile Island Accident (1979), the partial meltdown of the reactor core at the Three Mile Island nuclear power plant in Pennsylvania, USA, resulted in the release of a small number of radioactive substances. Although there were no immediate health effects, it raised concerns about nuclear safety [36]. Chernobyl Disaster (1986), an explosion and subsequent meltdown of the Chernobyl nuclear reactor in Ukraine resulted in a significant release of radioactive materials into the atmosphere, causing contamination and long-term health and environmental effects. This accident affected people living around the area of plant due to high radiation levels in local region. A large area

of Europe was affected by radioactivity. All living organisms that live 30 km from area were affected by the accident. Contaminated food consumption resulted in disease like thyroid cancer. The wildlife in the vicinity of the accident was badly affected [37]. Goiânia Accident (1987) in Brazil, a radioactive source possessing highly radioactive cesium-137 was left accidentally and later scavenged by people without knowing dangers associated with it. This led to radiation exposure, illnesses and several deaths [38]. Fukushima Disaster (2011) in Japan in which the Fukushima Daiichi nuclear power plant was seriously damaged by an tsumani earthquake, leading to meltdowns in reactors, resulted in the spread of radioactive materials, widespread evacuations and long-term effects on environment and raised multiple health concerns [39]. Other incidents include, Tokaimura nuclear accident, Marcoule nuclear accident, Pak nuclear accident, Mihama nuclear power plant accident and K-19 nuclear powered submarine [40].

Radioactivity effects on ecosystem and biodiversity

Radioactivity has significant impacts on ecosystems. When radioactive materials are released into the environment, whether via natural processes or human activities, they affect various components of ecosystem, such as plants, microorganisms and animals. Ecological relation between different components of ecosystem is disrupted by irradiation of plants and animals [41]. The radioactive properties of the soil layer, which is at the boundary of the lithosphere, hydrosphere and atmosphere, directly influence growth and survival of terrestrial flora and fauna [42]. After the radioactive accident, there was a rapid increment in radioactivity levels of seawater in result marine biota experienced elevated levels of radionuclide activities [43].

Ecosystem disruption

Radioactive contamination can disturb the delicate balance of ecosystems. The radioactive materials in soil, water and air can contaminate food sources which result in bioaccumulation and biomagnification. Biomagnification or bioaccumulation, occurs when living organisms accumulate certain chemicals at higher concentrations than their surrounding environment or the food they consume [44]. Radioactive substances can enter the food chain via plants, water and soil. Certain organisms like plants and algae absorb radioactive substances from the environment. These substances are then passed onto animals which consume these plants or other animals. This whole process can lead to bioaccumulation. In this way the concentration of radioactivity enhances as it goes up the food chain. Biomagnification occurs when higher-level predators accumulate high concentration of radioactivity because of consumption of multiple contaminated organisms. Radioactive contamination significantly affects the species population dynamics in an ecosystem. High levels of radiation exposure can lead to less reproductive success, high mortality rates and decrease in population sizes which disrupt the balance and diversity of species within an ecosystem. It can alter the behavior and distribution of organisms, effects their migration patterns, breeding habitats and ecological interactions within an

ecosystem. Alterations in population sizes or reproductive abilities of species can disrupt predator-prey relationships, resources competition and ecological niches. These disruptions can lead to collapse of entire ecosystem [41,45].

Genetic and cellular effects on organisms

Radioactivity can have detrimental effects on living organisms. When radioactive materials are released into the environment, organisms can be exposed to ionizing radiation, which can cause damage to DNA, cells and tissues. Radioactive materials can persist in the environment for extended periods, posing long-term risks to ecosystems. Some radioisotopes have long half-lives, which means they remain radioactive for thousands or millions of years making future organisms to be at risk of radioactive exposure. High level radiation exposure results in mutations, cell death or normal cell functioning impairment and overall health of radiation affected organisms. They also lead to acute radiation sickness, while prolonged exposure to lower levels may result in increased risks of cancers and reproductive abnormalities.

Radioactivity effects on plants

Plants being at the bottom of food chain, are specifically at the risk of radioactivity. Exposure to radiation can hinder their growth, disrupt photosynthesis and alter their reproductive processes, elevates genetic damage and mutation rates, reduces seed and pollen viability and increases the chance of developmental abnormalities. This can have cascading effects on the entire ecosystem, as plant productivity directly impacts herbivores, predators, and decomposers. There is variation in different taxa of plants in how they react to these effects and depends on amount and duration of exposure. There is a link between radiation and stressors in environment like heavy metals, drought and temperature etc. may have significant roles in influencing the vulnerability of plants to stress caused by radiation exposure [46]. Multiple studies have provided evidence that younger trees exhibit higher susceptibility to radiation effects, resulting in notable alterations in growth form and quality of wood [47,48]. A study revealed that the plants originating from Chernobyl area exhibited low germination rates in areas with higher contamination level, even when grown is carried out in controlled and uncontaminated environment [49]. A study was conducted focusing on fruit trees and bushes, butterflies and bumblebees in Chernobyl area. It was discovered that in highly radioactive regions, fruit-bearing plants produced fewer fruits, which is said to be related to the decline in pollinating insects and small size of trees. The reduced fruit production also impacted fruit-eating birds and caused hindrance in dispersal of seeds. This indicates a direct connection between radiation levels, frugivore abundance, pollinating insect populations and fruit production. The study showed that chronic radiation significantly affects the relationship between plant and animals and intricate interactions between species [50]. A common garden study was conducted in a radiation-free greenhouse using 660 seeds obtained from 33 wild carrots having previous exposure to radiation near Chernobyl nuclear power plant. Increased radia-

tion has detrimental impacts on seed germination timing and reduced germination rates. Furthermore, exposure to radiation also caused delays in later stages of development and the emergence of leaves [51]. The damage to the ecosystem by radiation from the Chernobyl nuclear power plant was investigated in forest areas. Due to high exposure of radiations the coniferous trees were killed. However, deciduous trees showed resistance and did not die but showed earlier loss of branches and leaves. Fruits trees were also contaminated by the radiations because the fruits showed the presence of radioactivity in them [52].

Impact of radioactivity on animals

Animals, including mammals, birds, insects, and aquatic species, can also suffer from the consequences of radioactivity. Elevated radiation levels can affect their immune systems, reproductive capabilities, and overall health. Some species may experience reduced population sizes or even face extinction due to the inability to adapt to radioactively contaminated environments. The existing levels of natural radioactivity can impact mutational input, thereby effecting genetic constitution and composition of natural populations [53]. A study was carried out on the impacts of radiation exposure on blood samples and bone marrow of Japanese macaques living near the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power plant which included 72 macaques captured within a 40-kilometer vicinity of the power plant and a control group containing 23 macaques non exposed to radiations. The results showed that high internal dose rates were linked with low white blood cells and platelet counts in mature macaques. The bone marrow samples indicated low hematopoietic cells, myeloid cells and megakaryocytes but high adipocytes counts when the internal dose in the femoral bone marrow of the mature macaques was elevated [54]. Gastrointestinal tract, skin, hematopoietic system, vascular system and spermatogenic cells are highly sensitive to radiation damage. Acute radiation syndrome occurs within 30 days of radiation exposure which has various effects like depletion of bone marrow and circulatory cells leading to hematopoietic syndrome, furthermore, it results in DNA double strand breaks, cutaneous injury, splenomegaly and brain hemorrhage. Radiation exposure activates pathways like iNOS/NF-kB/NF-IL6 and p53/Bax, which promotes DNA strand breaks, bacterial infection susceptibility, Toll-like receptors signaling, cytokine concentrations, cytochrome c release and depletion of NAD and ATP pools via poly-ADP ribose polymerase dependency. These alterations promote autophagy and apoptosis resulting in a high mortality rate. Chronic and severe radiation subjection can result in hematopoietic depletion which can be fatal without proper medical attention [55]. Animals models under acute radiation exposure in experimental laboratory resulted in various syndromes such as gastrointestinal acute radiation syndrome, hematopoietic acute radiation syndrome, neurological syndrome, cutaneous radiation syndrome and cardiovascular syndrome relying on radiation dose as well as other factors like air pressure, temperature and availability of water and food. These syndromes cause various alterations at molecular

level, including DNA impairment, inflammasome formation, alterations in microRNA-34a, activation of inducible nitric oxide synthase and cytokine/chemokine storms in circulation and tissues [56]. The interdependence and competition between species, especially among struggling species for food, is challenging for studying radiation sensitivity in laboratory. While some organisms show high sensitivity towards radiation in natural environments compared to laboratory environment. Understanding the underlying phenomena of this sensitivity is challenging to investigate in wild place and difficult to properly replicate in laboratory settings [57].

Effects on birds

Like other components of ecosystem, birds also suffer from the consequences of radioactivity. To investigate the effect of radiation on breeding birds in Fukushima Prefecture, a census was conducted from 2011 to 2014. The study aimed to assess whether the diversity and abundance of birds were gradually more influenced by radiation with the period of time. Decline in bird abundance was observed when radiation levels gone up, with significant variation between species. Despite a decrease in background radiation level over time, the negative relation between radiation and abundance became intense. However, with the increasing trophic levels this negative relationship weakened. The study revealed that the detrimental consequences of radiation on birds abundance and species diversity accumulate gradually over period of time [58]. Birds residing in highly contaminated places around Chernobyl exhibited reduced brain size, specifically reflected by decreased head volume which suggests that radioactive contamination has detrimental effects on normal brain development in birds [59].

Radiation effects on marine life

In year 2011, the Fukushima Daiichi nuclear power plant incident, triggered by an earthquake and tsunami, has raised concerns about the potential effects of radioactive water and particles on marine. This incident resulted in the direct release of radioactive particles into coastal ecosystem [60]. Fish are sensitive to radioactivity. Since Chernobyl disaster happened, the freshwater fish have been exceedingly manifested to radiation which showed morphological alterations in their reproductive process [61]. Cesium (^{137}Cs) bioaccumulation in fish muscles goes up with size in pike-perch, silver carp and catfish from Cooling Pond. Additionally, food web trophic levels are found to influence ^{137}Cs bioaccumulation. This suggests that larger fish and fishes occupying higher trophic levels may have higher level of ^{137}Cs in their muscle tissues [62]. Fish inhabiting lakes polluted by the Chernobyl accident have been observed to have frequent morphological alterations, particularly in their reproductive systems. These anomalies are documented to persist even after several generations affecting various fish species [63,64]. Ionizing radiation is known to cause DNA damage, but limited research has focused on studying the link between long-term exposure to environmental radionuclides and damage to DNA. In the case of a study conducted on catfish from the Cooling Pond, no

significant correlation was found between levels of radiation exposure and chromosomal injury [65]. Recent studies have indicated that dolphins and neon flying squid accumulated radioactive isotopes like $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$, ^{134}Cs and ^{137}Cs after the Fukushima Daichi Nuclear Power Plant Accident. However, it was noticed that accumulation level dropped over time. Assessment of radiation dosage suggested that the emitted radiation may be the reason of significant danger to these marine species in Northwest Pacific Ocean. Same findings were observed for neon flying squid [66]. Gametes and larvae are highly vulnerable to damage by radiation compared to adults. Among organisms, complex species like fish are generally less tolerant of radiation compared to simpler organisms like algae and bacteria. Benthic organisms that reside in or near sediment are susceptible to radiation effects compared to pelagic organisms in seawater because radioactive waste is absorbed and accumulated in sediment, being a greater risk to benthic organisms. Limited laboratory studies have explored the biological impacts of chronic radiation exposure on organisms because of variation in sensitivities among different species [67]. Studies on radiation impacts on marine organisms have shown limited targeted analysis on genotoxic effects. Jha et al. [68] performed laboratory assays on mussel *Mytilus edulis* to assess the genotoxic effects of tritium. They observed a dosage reliant response to single strand breaks of DNA and micronuclei, indicating genomic injury.

Health risks of radioactivity for humans

The growing trend of nuclear power intensifies the risks linked with industrial mishaps and nuclear violence. Ionizing radiation exposure disrupts stability of genome and gene expression, leading to disturbances in cellular and organ metabolism. High radiation exposure causes acute radiation syndrome, resulting in specific injuries to organs such as the hematopoietic, gastrointestinal and cerebrovascular systems [69]. Exposure to radiation in humans can lead to radiation poisoning, which cause various symptoms depending on the dose received. These symptoms may include destruction of blood cells and tissues, hemorrhaging, and in severe cases, even mortality [70]. Radioactivity induces chromosome lesions, tumors and minisatellite length mutations. A high-radiation coastal peninsula in Kerala, India, is said to have highest concentration of natural radioactivity in a highly populated place. A study of 248 pedigrees (988 individuals) from this area and control group from nearby low-radiation islands revealed the significant increased germ-line point mutations in the pedigrees living around high radiation. The mutations occurred at nucleotide positions [71]. Subjection to high concentrations of radiation, for instance being near to an atomic blast can result in skin burns and radiation sickness. This results in long haul health effects like cancer and cardiovascular diseases. Low level radiation exposure does not result in immediate health problems but acts as a small contributor to the overall risk of cancer. Fetuses and children are particularly vulnerable to damage by radiation exposure. Their dividing cells make them more susceptible to potential disturbance and damage caused by radiation. Comparative studies have revealed that humans show moderate sensitivity

to radiation induced mutations in comparison to other species. The persistence of the effect size over time indicates a lack of improvement in environmental conditions regarding radiation-induced mutations. Radioactive contamination has impact on the fitness of individuals in both present and coming generations, potentially leading to population-level consequences which may extend beyond boundaries of areas which are directly contaminated posing widespread and long-lasting radiation effects on biodiversity and ecosystems [72].

Organisms adaptation to radiation

With the passing time the radiation intensity in radioactive contaminated areas has gradually decreased. Some organisms have evolved specific adaptations over time that allow them to forbear and survive in environments with high radiation levels. These adaptations can occur at cellular, molecular and physiological level. Some organisms may have developed antioxidant systems to counteract the detrimental effects of reactive oxygen species generated by radiation. In certain cases, organisms inhabiting radioactive environments have undergone evolutionary changes, such as mutations in genes responsible for DNA repair or radiation sensing. These genetic alterations can provide enhanced resistance to radiation. The survival of pale grass blue butterflies in Fukushima, even in regions with low radiation doses is a potential example of adaptation to radiation [73]. Researchers conducted study on grasshoppers in the Chernobyl exclusion zone and discovered that offspring with faster maturation rates have higher levels of DNA destruction. The accelerated growth in these grasshoppers led to enhanced oxidative stress and subsequent injury. However, this adaptation allows them to reach maturity and reproduce prior to radiation exposure. These findings indicate a trade-off where the population is maintained at the expense of more damage to DNA, suggesting the presence of an adaptive strategy [74]. In later generations of *Drosophila*, the of sex-linked recessive lethal genes frequency was reduced compared to the early generations [75]. Such examples give an idea of the occurrence of adaptation to radiation.

Radioactive elements remediation

Due to the potential ecological risks of radioactivity, monitoring programs are often in place to assess the levels of radiation in different environmental compartments and organisms. In cases of contamination, remediation efforts may be necessary to reduce the exposure and mitigate the effects on ecosystems. The management of radioactive contaminants released into the environment is important to protect the balance and working of ecosystems. Strict measures and proper methods of disposal for radioactive waste are crucial to minimize or prevent the ecological effects of radioactivity. Various remediation technologies are being evolved to address the issue of radioactive contamination in the environment. These include physical methods such as extraction, precipitation and membrane separation, also chemical methods such as leaching, chemical extraction and hydrolysis. However, these technologies are not cost effective and suitable to work only for small-scale contamination. Phytoremediation and microbial

bioremediation have emerged as effective and economical large-scale approaches to remove radiation pollution. Phytoremediation is harnessing plants to eliminate radioactive pollutants from different environments, while microbial bioremediation involves bacteria and fungi for the same purpose. Some plants and microorganisms are known as potential accumulators of radioactive materials Their complete bioremediation mechanisms remain unknown [5].

Conclusion

Radioactivity poses significant impacts on ecosystem by directly affecting biodiversity and functioning of ecological systems. The discharge of radioactive substances into the environment, whether through natural processes or anthropogenic activities, can lead to alterations in soil, water and air quality which have potential to alter the distribution, abundance and behavior of organisms within ecosystems. Radiation can directly affect the health and survival of organisms, causing genetic mutations, physiological disturbance and even population declines. Some organisms have shown remarkable resilience and the ability to adapt to radiation stress over time. The effects of radiation on biodiversity are not limited to individual organisms. There can be cascading impacts throughout the food chain, as radiation can accumulate and magnify in different trophic levels. This can lead to bioaccumulation and biomagnification of radionuclides, posing additional risks to higher-level consumers, including humans. Understanding interactions between radioactivity, ecosystems and biodiversity is vital for effective environmental management and conservation efforts. It requires interdisciplinary research, including radiation biology, ecology and genetics to assess the long-term consequences and develop strategies for radiation mitigation. Continued research and monitoring efforts, combined with responsible management of radioactive materials, are essential for mitigating the risks and protecting both natural environments and human well-being.

References

1. Rasmussen, J., & Ellis P. (2023). Radioactivity. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/science/radioactivity>.
2. Kaur, G., & Singh, J. (2019). Effects of Radiation on the Environment. In *Radiation Effects in Polymeric Materials*. Springer International Publishing. p. 1-34.
3. Rahman, S., Faheem, M., & Matiullah. (2008). Natural radioactivity measurements in Pakistan-an overview. *Journal of Radiological Protection*, 28(4), 443.
4. Adebisi, F.M., Ore, O.T., Adeola, A.O., Durodola, S.S., Akeremale, O.F., Olubodun, K.O., & Akeremale, O.K. (2021). Occurrence and remediation of naturally occurring radioactive materials in Nigeria: a review. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, 19(4), 3243-3262.
5. Singh, G., Bhadange, S., Bhawna, F., Shewale, P., Dahiya, R., Aggarwal, A., Manju, F., & Arya, S.K. (2023). Phytoremediation of radioactive elements, possibilities and challenges: special focus on

- agricultural aspects. *International Journal of Phytoremediation*, 25(1), 1-8.
6. Saenen, E., Horemans, N., Vanhoudt, N., Vandenhove, H., Biermans, G., Van Hees, M., Wannijn, J., Vangronsveld, J., & Cuypers, A. (2013). Effects of pH on uranium uptake and oxidative stress responses induced in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 32(9), 2125-2133.
7. Dushenkov, S. (2003). Trends in phytoremediation of radionuclides. *Plant and Soil*, 249, 167-175.
8. Sokolik, G., Ovsianikova, S., Voinikava, K., Ivanova, T., & Papenia, M. (2014). Biological availability of ²³⁸U, ²³⁴U and ²²⁶Ra for wild berries and meadow grasses in natural ecosystems of Belarus. *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity*, 127, 155-162.
9. Radvanyi, P., & Villain, J. (2017). The discovery of radioactivity. *Comptes Rendus Physique*, 18(9), 544-550.
10. Becquerel, H. (1896). Sur les radiations émises par phosphorescence. *Comptes rendus de l'Academie des Sciences, Paris*, 122, 420-421.
11. Debierne, A. (1899). Sur une nouvelle matière radio-active. *Comptes rendus*, 129(16), 593-595.
12. Schmidt, G.C. (1898). Ueber die von den Thorverbindungen und einigen anderen Substanzen ausgehende Strahlung. *Annalen der Physik*, 301(5), 141-151.
13. Curie, I. (1934). Un nouveau type de radioactivité. *Comptes rendus des seances de l'Academie des sciences (CRAS)*, 198, 254-256.
14. Joliot, F., & Curie, I. (1934). Un nouveau type de radioactivité. *CR Acad. Sci. Paris*, 198, 254-256.
15. Lorenz, E. (1944). Radioactivity and lung cancer; a critical review of lung cancer in the miners of Schneeberg and Joachimsthal. *Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, 5(1), 1-15.
16. Hoover, H. C. (1950). *Georgius Agricola De Re Metallica. Рупол Классик*, (In Russ).
17. Scheminzky, F., & Schroecksadel, H. (1961). Influence of radium emanation on heart frequency and blood pressure. *Wiener klinische Wochenschrift*, 73, 123-127.
18. Eisenbud, M., & Gesell, T.F. (1997). *Environmental radioactivity from natural, industrial and military sources: from natural, industrial and military sources*. Elsevier.
19. Gunderman, R.B., & Gonda, A.S. (2015). Radium girls. *Radiology*, 274(2), 314-318.
20. Belyaev, A., Ross, D., Belyaev, A., & Ross, D. (2021). Radioactivity. *The Basics of Nuclear and Particle Physics*, 67-88.
21. L'Annunziata, M.F. (2012). *Handbook of radioactivity analysis*. Academic press.
22. Commission, C.N.S. (2020). *Natural background radiation*. <https://nuclearsafety.gc.ca/eng/resources/fact-sheets/natural-background-radiation.cfm#:~:text=According%20to%20the%20United%20Nations,radionuclides%20through%20inhalation%20and%20ingestion>.
23. Dosh, R.J., Hasan, A.K., & Abojassim, A.A. (2023). Natural radioactivity for soil samples in primary schools at Najaf city, Iraq. *Applied Radiation and Isotopes*, 197, 110830.
24. Abojassim, A.A., & Rasheed, L.H. (2021). Natural radioactivity of soil in the Baghdad governorate. *Environmental Earth Sciences*, 80, 1-13.
25. Engelbrecht, R. (2020). Environmental radioactivity monitoring. In *Handbook of Radioactivity Analysis: Volume 2*. Elsevier. p. 1-40.
26. Gómez, M., Suursoo, S., Martin-Sanchez, N., Vaasma, T., & Leier, M. (2023). Natural radioactivity in European drinking water: A review. *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology*, 53(2), 198-215.
27. Martin, R., Dowling, K., Pearce, D., Sillitoe, J., & Florentine, S. (2014). Health effects associated with inhalation of airborne arsenic arising from mining operations. *Geosciences*, 4(3), 128-175.
28. Keith, S., Doyle, J.R., Harper, C., Mumtaz, M., Tarrago, O., Wohlers, D.W., Diamond, G.L., Citra, M., & Barber, L.E. (2013). Toxicological profile for radon. Atlanta (GA): Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (US).
29. Hu, Q.-H., Weng, J.-Q., & Wang, J.-S. (2010). Sources of anthropogenic radionuclides in the environment: a review. *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity*, 101(6), 426-437.
30. Oforiwa, P. (2021). Nuclear emergency: A review of radioactivity in human ecosystem. *LC International Journal of STEM*, 2(1), 1-8.
31. Burkitbayev, M., Priest, N., Mitchell, P., Vintro, L., Pourcelot, L., Kuyanov, Y., & Artemyev, O. (2011). Ecological impacts of large-scale war preparations: Semipalatinsk test site, Kazakhstan. *Warfare Ecology: A New Synthesis for Peace and Security*.
32. Beresford, N., Fesenko, S., Konoplev, A., Skuterud, L., Smith, J., & Voigt, G. (2016). Thirty years after the Chernobyl accident: What lessons have we learnt? *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity*, 157, 77-89.
33. Loge, L., Florescu, C., Alves, A., & Menahem, B. (2020). Radiation enteritis: diagnostic and therapeutic issues. *Journal of Visceral Surgery*, 157(6), 475-485.
34. Martin, D.R., & Semelka, R.C. (2006). Health effects of ionising radiation from diagnostic CT. *The Lancet*, 367(9524), 1712-1714.
35. Akleyev, A., Krestinina, L.Y., Degteva, M., & Tolstykh, E. (2017). Consequences of the radiation accident at the Mayak production association in 1957 (the 'Kyshtym Accident'). *Journal of Radiological Protection*, 37(3), R19.
36. Island, U. (1979). *Report of the President's Commission on the Accident at Three Mile Island: The need for change: The legacy of TMI* (Vol. 41). The Commission.
37. Cannon, G., & Kiang, J.G. (2022). A review of the impact on the ecosystem after ionizing irradiation: wildlife population. *International Journal of Radiation Biology*, 98(6), 1054-1062.

38. Roberts, L. (1987). Radiation Accident Grips Goiânia: The Brazilian government is grappling with the second worst radiation accident in history and is looking into the role of bone marrow specialist Robert Gale in treating the victims. *Science*, 238(4830), 1028-1031.
39. Nakamura, A., & Kikuchi, M. (2011). What we know, and what we have not yet learned: Triple disasters and the Fukushima nuclear fiasco in Japan. *Public Administration Review*, 71(6), 893-899.
40. Sobhi, M.A., & Othman, S.A. (2019). Kyshtym Nuclear Accident. *Radiation Biophysics*, 95.
41. Geras'kin, S.A. (2016). Ecological effects of exposure to enhanced levels of ionizing radiation. *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity*, 162-163, 347-357.
42. Jabarov, E. (2022). Radioactivity of clay minerals of the oil-bearing Apsheron Peninsula. *Azerbaijan Chemical Journal*, 1, 51-54.
43. Aono, T., Ito, Y., Sohtome, T., Mizuno, T., Igarashi, S., Kanda, J., & Ishimaru, T. (2014). Observation of radionuclides in marine biota off the coast of Fukushima prefecture after TEPCO's Fukushima Daiichi nuclear power station accident. In *Radiation Monitoring and Dose Estimation of the Fukushima Nuclear Accident*. p. 115-123.
44. Bienfang, P.K., Trapido-Rosenthal, H., & Laws, E.A. (2013). Bioaccumulation/Biomagnifications in Food Chains. In *Environmental Toxicology: Selected Entries from the Encyclopedia of Sustainability Science and Technology*. Springer New York. p. 35-69.
45. Nenciu, M., Oros, A., Roşioru, D., Galatchi, M., Filimon, A., Tiganov, G., Danilov, C., & Roşoiu, N. (2016). Heavy metal bioaccumulation in marine organisms from the Romanian Black Sea coast. *Academy of Romanian Scientists*, 5(1), 38-52.
46. Mousseau, T.A., & Møller, A.P. (2020). Plants in the light of ionizing radiation: What have we learned from Chernobyl, Fukushima, and other "hot" places? *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 11, 552.
47. Mousseau, T.A., Welch, S.M., Chizhevsky, I., Bondarenko, O., Milinevsky, G., Tedeschi, D.J., Bonisoli-Alquati, A., & Møller, A.P. (2013). Tree rings reveal extent of exposure to ionizing radiation in Scots pine *Pinus sylvestris*. *Trees*, 27, 1443-1453.
48. Tulik, M., & Rusin, A. (2005). Microfibril angle in wood of Scots pine trees (*Pinus sylvestris*) after irradiation from the Chernobyl nuclear reactor accident. *Environmental Pollution*, 134(2), 195-199.
49. Møller, A., & Mousseau, T. (2017). Radiation levels affect pollen viability and germination among sites and species at Chernobyl. *International Journal of Plant Sciences*, 178(7), 1.
50. Møller, A.P., Barnier, F., & Mousseau, T.A. (2012). Ecosystems effects 25 years after Chernobyl: pollinators, fruit set and recruitment. *Oecologia*, 170, 1155-1165.
51. Boratyński, Z., Arias, J.M., Garcia, C., Mappes, T., Mousseau, T.A., Møller, A.P., Pajares, A.J.M., Piwczyński, M., & Tukulenko, E. (2016). Ionizing radiation from Chernobyl affects development of wild carrot plants. *Scientific Reports*, 6(1), 1-8.
52. Nakanishi, T.M., & Tanoi, K. (2016). *Agricultural implications of the Fukushima nuclear accident: the first three years*. Springer Nature.
53. Møller, A.P., & Mousseau, T.A. (2013). The effects of natural variation in background radioactivity on humans, animals and other organisms. *Biological Reviews*, 88(1), 226-254.
54. Urushihara, Y., Suzuki, T., Shimizu, Y., Ohtaki, M., Kuwahara, Y., Suzuki, M., Uno, T., Fujita, S., Saito, A., & Yamashiro, H. (2018). Haematological analysis of Japanese macaques (*Macaca fuscata*) in the area affected by the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant accident. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1), 1-10.
55. Kiang, J.G., & Olabisi, A.O. (2019). Radiation: a poly-traumatic hit leading to multi-organ injury. *Cell & Bioscience*, 9(1), 25.
56. Williams, J.P., Brown, S.L., Georges, G.E., Hauer-Jensen, M., Hill, R.P., Huser, A.K., Kirsch, D.G., MacVittie, T.J., Mason, K.A., & Medhora, M.M. (2010). Animal models for medical countermeasures to radiation exposure. *Radiation Research*, 173(4), 557-578.
57. Garnier-Laplace, J., Geras' kin S., Della-Vedova C. et al. (2013). Are radiosensitivity data derived from natural field conditions consistent with data from controlled exposures? A case study of Chernobyl wildlife chronically exposed to low dose rates. *J. Environ. Radioact*, 121, 12.
58. Møller, A.P., Nishiumi, I., & Mousseau, T.A. (2015). Cumulative effects of radioactivity from Fukushima on the abundance and biodiversity of birds. *Journal of Ornithology*, 156(1), 297-305.
59. Møller, A.P., Bonisoli-Alquati, A., Rudolfson, G., & Mousseau, T.A. (2011). Chernobyl Birds Have Smaller Brains. *PLOS ONE*, 6(2), e16862.
60. Vives i Batlle, J. (2011). Impact of nuclear accidents on marine biota. *Integrated Environmental Assessment and Management*, 7(3), 365-367.
61. Lerebours, A.I., Gudkov, D., Nagorskaya, L., Kaglyan, A., Rizevski, V., Leshchenko, A., Bailey, E.H., Bakir, A., Ovsyanikova, S., & Laptev, G. (2018). Impact of environmental radiation on the health and reproductive status of fish from Chernobyl. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 52(16), 9442-9450.
62. Kryshev, I. (1995). Radioactive contamination of aquatic ecosystems following the Chernobyl accident. *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity*, 27(3), 207-219.
63. Belova, N., & Emel'yanova, N. (2009). Status of the reproductive system of bony fish from the Teterev River and the Kiev Reservoir 20 years after the Chernobyl accident. *Journal of Ichthyology*, 49, 793-802.
64. Belova, N., Emel'yanova, N., Makeeva, A., & Ryabov, I. (2007). The state of the reproductive system of several fish species from water bodies polluted with radionuclides during the Chernobyl catastrophe. *Journal of Ichthyology*, 47, 366-384.
65. Sugg, D.W., Brooks, J.A., Jagoe, C.H., Smith, M.H., Chesser, R.K., Bickham, J.W., Lomakin, M.D., Dallas, C.E., & Baker, R.J. (1996). DNA damage and radiocesium in channel catfish from Chernobyl.

Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry: An International Journal, 15(7), 1057-1063.

66. Men, W., Wang, F., Yu, W., He, J., Lin, F., & Deng, F. (2020). Impact of the Fukushima Dai-ichi Nuclear Power Plant Accident on the neon flying squids in the Northwest Pacific from 2011 to 2018. *Environmental Pollution*, 264, 114647.

67. i Batlle, J.V., Aono, T., Brown, J. E., Hosseini, A., Garnier-Laplace, J., Sazykina, T., Steenhuisen, F., & Strand, P. (2014). The impact of the Fukushima nuclear accident on marine biota: retrospective assessment of the first year and perspectives. *Science of the Total Environment*, 487, 143-153.

68. Jha, A.N., Dogra, Y., Turner, A., & Millward, G.E. (2005). Impact of low doses of tritium on the marine mussel, *Mytilus edulis*: genotoxic effects and tissue-specific bioconcentration. *Mutation Research/Genetic Toxicology and Environmental Mutagenesis*, 586(1), 47-57.

69. Shakyawar, S.K., Mishra, N.K., Vellichirammal, N.N., Cary, L., Helikar, T., Powers, R., Oberley-Deegan, R.E., Berkowitz, D.B., Bayles, K.W., & Singh, V.K. (2023). A Review of radiation-induced alterations of multi-omic profiles, radiation injury biomarkers, and countermeasures. *Radiation Research*, 199(1), 89-111.

70. Guskova, A., Baranov, A., & Gusev, I. (2001). Acute radiation sickness: underlying principles and assessment. CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, USA.

71. Forster, L., Forster, P., Lutz-Bonengel, S., Willkomm, H., & Brinkmann, B. (2002). Natural radioactivity and human mitochondrial DNA mutations. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 99(21), 13950-13954.

72. Møller, A.P., & Mousseau, T.A. (2015). Strong effects of ionizing radiation from Chernobyl on mutation rates. *Scientific Reports*, 5(1), 8363.

73. Taira, W., Hiyama, A., Nohara, C., Sakauchi, K., & Otaki, J.M. (2015). Ingestional and transgenerational effects of the Fukushima nuclear accident on the pale grass blue butterfly. *Journal of radiation research*, 56(suppl_1), i2-i18.

74. Bonisoli-Alquati, A., Ostermiller, S., Beasley, D.A.E., Welch, S.M., Møller, A.P., & Mousseau, T.A. (2018). Faster development covaries with higher DNA damage in grasshoppers (*Chorthippus albomarginatus*) from Chernobyl. *Physiological and Biochemical Zoology*, 91(2), 776-787.

75. Hancock, S., Vo, N.T., Byun, S.H., Zainullin, V.G., Seymour, C.B., & Mothersill, C. (2019). Effects of historic radiation dose on the frequency of sex-linked recessive lethals in *Drosophila* populations following the Chernobyl nuclear accident. *Environmental Research*, 172, 333-337.